

DESIGN OF AN AUTOMOBILE BODY PANEL MANUFACTURED BY RESIN TRANSFER MOULDING

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ABSTRACT

The Resin Transfer Moulding technology may be used for the manufacturing of external body panels in the automotive industry as high surface quality (Class A) is being obtained by using certain resin and reinforcement systems.

This paper assesses a case study on the design and analysis of a body panel for an utility car, materialised on a front wing which is at present manufactured on steel for the long series and in thermoplastic for the short series sporting version. An economic evaluation was also performed in order to assess the feasibility of this manufacturing technique and the optimum size of the series to be produced.

Keywords: Body panel, Design, Resin Transfer Moulding, Wing.

1.INTRODUCTION

During the last decade of the XX Century the basic concept of what a vehicle is supposed to be will remain almost the same. Future developments will be focused on the security and comfort improvement, including also lower cost, component reliability and reduction of the environmental pollution (1).

The automotive industry is at present at the top of a technological wave where new materials and designs offer such possibilities that manufacturers must take them under consideration (2). The composite materials are included in these new materials with the following advantages : weight reduction, corrosion resistance, aesthetics and style, isolation and the ability to integrate several parts into one single component (3).

The main characteristics of the composite market are the industrial demands and the cost reductions, together with the transforming methods used. Of special relevance is the molding by Resin Transfer Moulding (RTM) where the reinforcement is placed in a mold and injection of the resin takes place in liquid condition. To consider all these processes as definitively implanted in the automotive market it is necessary to specifically develop and design the molding and preforming processes, the equipments, molds, finishing, resins and reinforcements. This will result in cost reductions, enhanced productivity and manufacturing of parts with the required specifications.

2. DESIGN METHODOLOGY

The composite materials have their own design philosophy resulting from the possibility of certain physical and mechanical properties to be tailored to design requirements. Profitability of the material is therefore improved in factors such as manufacturing cost, weight and performance.

However, only plastic versions of previous designs are obtained quite often as a consequence of wrong exploitation of the above mentioned potential. This occurs mainly with metal designs which are to be replaced.

This is quite obvious with certain specific designing practices that both experience and requirements of the conventional production methods (shaping, machining, welding, injection, etc...) have turned into usual and that when designing with composites lose their sense. The wide variety of designing procedures embraces aspects such as thickness and minimum shaping radius, security factors and bonding systems between components. Such mentioned philosophy gives a more complex design resulting from the introduction of new variables associated to non-homogeneity properties of the materials.

Fig. 1 shows the activity sequence to be carried out during the design phase of a generic component, which has been followed for the particular case of the front wing.

The first step to be taken when designing a product is to prepare a list of specifications with all the requirements to be met and the different data necessary for its elaboration and creation. In this case the specification book from Renault for the thermoplastic wing was used.

The most relevant specifications concerning this case are those related to dimensional stability with temperature and strength and stiffness under in-service conditions, included impact.

Once specifications are known these must be verified on the designed component either by numerical methods whenever simulation is possible or by tests performed over specimens of the material used.

Depending on such structural analysis or tests the necessary modifications to the components will lead to the final production design. Manufacturing toolings will be made according to this design and different prototypes will be made for studying the process feasibility, with the subsequent slight modifications to the component in order to improve the production phase.

Figure 1. Design methodology.

3. PRELIMINARY DESIGN

In this phase a first designing approach is made according to data included in the specification book. The information available concerning the part to be designed, and the production processes and means to be used by the potential component manufacturers are also factors taken into account when designing.

3.1. Material selection.

A material data base was used for the material selection with the different information included concerning those resins and reinforcements open to RTM and SRIM transforming processes.

Among the resins taken into account are the unsaturated polyesters, epoxys, poliurethanes and vinylesther. Due to the lack of both structural relevance and important loads on the wing it was decided to use a polyester resin which offers enough mechanical properties for such commitment. This would result in a lower cost apart from other considerations such as surface finishing and temperature to be used.

The reinforcement selected was glass fiber mat, with a relatively low cost and considered as suitable if mechanical properties with high performances are not required, which is the case of the wing.

Therefore, the selection of the materials resulted in the polyester/fiber glass election as the most suitable one in the wing.

3.2. Design concept trade-off.

Two alternative design concepts for manufacturing were considered:

Version 1

The wing is manufactured in one single piece. Preforming is to be done in two parts. Both preforms overlap in the RTM mold followed by the resin injection. By such means the whole part would be obtained and only finishing operations would have to be carried out (edging, boring, etc...).

Version 2

Two preforms are done basically in the same way as Version 1. However, each part is separately injected. Both parts are then bonded together subsequently to finishing.

Both described processes are schematically shown in fig 2. Tables I and II show the most important aspects of each version. Basically, it must be outlined that while version 1 requires three manufacturing steps in two stages (preforming and injection), version 2 needs five steps in three stages (adding bonding to the above mentioned stages).

The advantage of version 1 is the lower quantity of steps and tooling to be used, while the main disadvantage would be a more complex and expensive injection due to the geometry of the entire part, as the injection tooling becomes more complex.

The critical step of version 1 would be the injection process (preforms placing, injection time, curing and stripping, mold cleaning, etc...). However, molding time in version 2 would be lower due to the simplicity of parts, although it must be taken parallel injections.

Figure 2 . Alternative design concepts.

In general, the design of a component can not be envisaged without considering the conception of the production tools, as designing viability depends on them. Another aspect to take under consideration is the value given by user with respect to the design. For instance, the user may consider as not useful to make parts with adhesive joints due to reasons such as quality control, service behaviour, etc...

	PHASE 1	PHASE 2	PHASE 3
VERSION 1	PREFORMING 1 PREFORMING 2	INJECTION	
VERSION 2	PREFORMING 1 PREFORMING 2	INJECTION 1 INJECTION 2	BONDING

Table I.

VERSION 1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * 2 Phases * 3 Phases * 3 Molds (2 preforming, 1 injection) * More complex injection mould * Injection time is a critical factor
VERSION 2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * 3 Phases * 5 Steps * 5 Molds (2 preforming, 2 injections, 1 bonding) * More simple injection tools * Bonding phase is a critical factor

Table II.

All of the above mentioned aspects must be studied and compared with respect to both production rates and costs in order to choose the proper designing concept. Therefore, a feasibility study was carried out involving part manufacturers and end user, resulting in the selection of version 1 (i.e. one single part wing) mainly due to its lower cost. Therefore, the design process was focused on this version.

4. FINAL DESIGN

Once the design concept to be used was defined, the next step was to make the final design starting from a tridimensional wing model generated from the aerodynamical geometric surface of the component and the interfaces with other components of the vehicle such as the frame, door, bumpers, etc.

From such tridimensional model, the following activities were performed:

- Development of a Finite Element Model for structural analysis.
- Drafting of the production drawings.
- Drafting of the molds for the preforming and injection processes.

The first two activities were carried out simultaneously, the first one acting as support and justification of the second one.

4.1 Structural analysis and design validation.

Fig. 3 shows the model used for Finit Element Analysis. It is formed by 646 thin shell elements. Mechanical properties (included tensile, compressive, shear, flexure and bearing) of the resin/reinforcement system were obtained by performing mechanical testing to specimens from injected flat panels. Such properties together with the laminate definition were introduced into the F.E.M.

According to the specification book, the following load cases were simulated:

- Side load applied to verify collapsing strength.
- Vertical load due to bonnet closing.(See fig. 4)
- Static strength of the assembly.

Figure 3. Finite Element Model.

Figure 4. Analysis of the bonnet closing load case

Such analysis allowed to check the wing strength and stiffness and to define the required thicknesses and fibre content, resulting on a part weight of 1.63 Kg.

To complete the F.E.A. impact and dimensional stability tests were performed. Impact behaviour proved very good under the specified conditions (up to 14.5Km/h with a 6Kg weight). Dimensional stability under 130°/10min conditions was excellent as well, showing no appreciable post-contraction.

Finally the thermal expansion was assessed with a resulting CTE of 0.43mm/m. The difference to the steel CTE was not so big that it could not be absorbed by the assembly, therefore a special fastening system was not required as it is for the thermoplastic wing.

4. CONCLUSIONS

In general the RTM process has a lower investment costs (equipment and moulds) and higher unitary costs (raw materials and manpower) than other possible composites transformation processes (SMC and thermoplastic injection).

This can be observed in the following graphic : costs vs. number of parts produced.

Figure 5. Process costs comparison

In the case of the wing, it can be said that the RTM process would be competitive for yields around 18,000 pieces/year. To obtain the 30,000 pieces/year expected by the car manufacturer two metallic moulds must be used, thus increasing the fixed costs. Therefore the RTM process would not be adequate for making this piece.

In any case, it would be necessary to optimize the process in order to minimize the transformation cycle and to reduce the investment required, for example using composite moulds. Efforts are being made at present to achieve these goals.

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